

Chimera State in Locally Coupled q -deformed Lozi Maps

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In this work, we explore the possibility of chimera states in the locally coupled q -deformed Lozi maps. The deformation is introduced using the Jaganathan-Sinha q -deformation scheme, which modifies the local map while smoothly recovering the standard Lozi map in the limit $q \rightarrow 1$. We observe that the q -deformed map exhibits significant modifications in its dynamical behavior compared to the standard case. Through analytical considerations and numerical simulations, we analyze fixed points, stability, bifurcation structure, and routes to chaos as functions of the deformation parameter. Chimera states are represented by stable coexisting synchronous and asynchronous domains in a lattice of coupled identical oscillators promoted by non-local or global coupling. An analogous 'spatial intermittency' is also observed in coupled map lattices. This work demonstrates that chimera states are not restricted to oscillatory systems or standard maps, but can also emerge in discrete-time systems with rationally deformed dynamics under purely local interactions. This indicates that chimera states are a robust and generic feature of a wide class of non-linear systems.

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1. Introduction

The idea of q -deformation originated in mathematical physics from investigations of Lie groups and Lie algebras, and it gave rise to quantum groups, which can be viewed as q -deformed analogues of universal enveloping algebras. These deformations modify the underlying algebraic relations while preserving much of their structure. Over the time, q -deformation has been applied beyond pure algebra, notably in quantum groups and non-extensive statistical mechanics, where the deformation parameter q serves as a key element in extending and generalising classical theoretical

frameworks [1–3].

This inherent non-uniqueness in the process of generalisation naturally extends to q -deformation as well. Any mathematical quantity, operator, or function does not have to be uniquely defined in order to be generalised [4]. There are several ways to construct q -deformations. For instance, two different approaches exist for defining the q -exponential function [5]. There exist definitions for q -logarithms [6], q -Gaussian [7], q -factorials and q -binomial coefficients [8, 9]. This generalisation is interesting from a mathematical perspective as well [10, 11]. It is anticipated that coupled oscillators with global or non-local connections may benefit from such generalisations [12–14].

Jagannathan and Sinha [15] gave the definition of q -deformation of numbers, to present

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a method for q -deformation of nonlinear maps. They examined the logistic map. One intriguing discovery was that, unlike one-dimensional maps, q -deformed logistic maps show the co-existence of attractors. Similar co-existing attractors were discovered by Patidar [16] for q -deformed Gaussian maps. Subsequent research examined the q -deformed Henon map [17] and Henon-like map [18]. In addition, the q -deformed cubic map [19], the Ricker map [20], and the Lorenz map [21] have been studied. The tri-trophic population dynamics model was enhanced and modified using the q -deformation [22]. It has found applications in areas such as encryption [23, 24]. According to Iyengar and Balakrishnan, image encryption can be achieved through even a slight change in the q -deformation parameter or the initial conditions, as such variations shift the system onto a different attractor [23].

Apart from multistability, q -deformed maps possess features that are particularly conducive to the emergence of chimera states in coupled systems. The q -deformation often transforms a nonlinear map into a rational function, introducing singularities and strongly fragmented basins of attraction. As a result, identical maps initialised with different initial conditions can evolve toward distinct dynamical behaviours. In addition, q -deformation can extend the domain of the map beyond a bounded interval, enriching the phase space structure. These properties facilitate the stable coexistence of coherent and incoherent dynamics, a hallmark of chimera states in coupled map lattices.

Chimera states were first reported by Kuramoto and Battogtokh in 2002 [25]. They observed that the identical oscillators can split into synchronised and desynchronised regions. This coexistence challenges the traditional assumptions about symmetry and stability in dynamical systems. Though this term has not been used, the same observations were made by Kaneko in the context of the coupled map lattice. He studied globally coupled logistic maps [26]. This work has been followed by many other works

in coupled maps, and 'spatial intermittency' is used to describe it [27–30]. Spatiotemporal chaos is observed in the network when the maps are coupled locally. On the other hand, with a significant value of coupling strength, a complete, coherent, and chaotic state is obtained in the network when the coupling is global or at least non-local. For local coupling, a synchronised fixed point can appear. Its stability can be studied using standard methods [31].

Yao *et al.* investigated the robustness of chimera states in complex dynamical systems and demonstrated that chimeras can persist under various forms of perturbations, including parameter mismatch, noise, and heterogeneity [32]. Kundu *et al.* [33] demonstrated the existence of chimera patterns in three-dimensional systems with purely local (nearest-neighbour) coupling, showing that neither non-local interactions nor low dimensionality are necessary for their formation. Similarly, Clerc *et al.* [34] reported chimera-type states arising solely from local coupling, indicating that spatial coexistence of coherent and incoherent dynamics can emerge through symmetry-breaking mechanisms in extended dynamical systems. Together, these studies establish that chimera states can robustly exist without requiring weak coupling or non-local connections, highlighting their generality across different coupling strengths and topologies.

Our work focuses on a lattice of coupled q -deformed Lozi maps, where the local dynamics is rationally modified using the Jaganathan-Sinha scheme. The deformation parameter significantly reshapes the phase-space and bifurcation structure, offering an additional control mechanism for chimera formation. Consequently, our results demonstrate that chimera states can persist in discrete-time systems with deformed local dynamics, further extending their generality beyond conventional frameworks.

Coupled map lattices (CML) are a popular class of models frequently used to describe the spatio-temporal phenomenon [35]. CML has

been widely researched throughout the last three decades. Due to their high computing capacity and potential for greater analytical tractability, CMLs are frequently employed in a variety of fields such as engineering, mathematics, and biology [36]. A CML is a system made up of many sites arranged on a lattice. Each site evolves in time according to the same local map, which describes its individual dynamics. At every time step, the state of a site is also influenced by a fixed set of neighboring sites through a prescribed coupling rule. Coupled sine circle maps have been shown to exhibit chimera states in two-population networks, where each group interacts through intra- and inter-group couplings [37, 38]. The formation of chimeras depends on initial conditions and parameters such as non-linearity (K) and frequency (Ω), with transitions observed from full coherence to clustered chimera and eventually to full chimera states. Even with entirely random initial conditions, partial synchronisation in one group and incoherence in the other can give rise to robust chimera patterns [38]. These studies demonstrate that coupled map lattices can support a wide variety of chimera behaviours, controlled by coupling, initial conditions, and system parameters.

2. Lozi Map

The Lozi map is a well-known discrete chaotic attractor map widely studied for its rich dynamical properties. Its applications span cryptography, electronic devices like memristors, optimisation, synchronisation, secure communications, AI with swarm intelligence, and more. The map's piecewise linear nature has allowed mathematicians to rigorously demonstrate its chaotic behaviour [39]. Key dynamical features, particularly in the conservative case ($|b| = 1$), include fixed points, invariant manifolds, basins of attraction, and the domain of strange attractors [40]. Recent studies have explored fractional and complex fractional versions of the Lozi map [41], including

q -deformed variants, where multistability and chaotic synchronisation in coupled systems have been observed [42].

Notably, coupled q -deformed Lozi maps can exhibit chimera states, where coherent and incoherent dynamics coexist. While synchronisation in coupled oscillators has been extensively studied [42, 43], research on chimera states is more recent. Here, we study the emergence of chimera states in a one-dimensional network of Lozi maps with local symmetric coupling.

3. q -deformed Lozi map

The 1-D CML model proposed by Kaneko is as follows:

$$x_{t+1}(i) = (1 - \epsilon)f(x_t(i)) \times \frac{\epsilon}{2} [f(x_t(i+1)) + f(x_t(i-1))]. \quad (1)$$

Here $x_t(i)$ is the i^{th} continuous variable at discrete time t . ϵ is the coupling strength. The value of variable $x(i)$ at time $t + 1$ depends upon its own state and the state of its nearest neighbour on either side at time t . The underlying map $f(x)$ is a 1-D map. The model can be extended to 2-D. The 2-D Lozi map is as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_{(t+1)} &= f(x_t, y_t) = 1 - a|x_t| + y_t, \\ y_{(t+1)} &= g(x_t, y_t) = bx_t, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

where the control parameters a and $b \neq 0$ are real constants. The Lozi map displays a singular hyperbolic chaotic attractor for $a = 1.7$ and $b = 0.5$.

We use the q -deformation scheme proposed by Jaganathan and Sinha [15]. The q -deformation scheme proposed by Jaganathan and Sinha is a method for systematically modifying discrete nonlinear maps by introducing a deformation parameter q (can be implemented via $d = 1 - q$), so that the map's functional form depends on a q -deformed version of the state variable. In this scheme, a standard map $x_{t+1} = f(x_t)$ is replaced

by $x_{t+1}=f([x_t]_q)$ where $[x]_q$ is a q -deformed value of x constructed using a deformation inspired by the Tsallis q -exponential such that the undeformed map is recovered in the limit $q \rightarrow 1$ ($d \rightarrow 0$). In the similar manner, the doubly q -deformed Lozi map is as follows [42]:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_{(t+1)} &= f([x_t]_{q_x}, [y_t]_{q_y}), \\ y_{(t+1)} &= g([x_t]_{q_x}, [y_t]_{q_y}), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where

$$[x]_{q_x} = \frac{x}{1 + (1 - q_x)(1 - x)}, \quad (4)$$

$$[y]_{q_y} = \frac{y}{1 + (1 - q_y)(1 - y)}. \quad (5)$$

Here, we study a particular case where $q_x = q_y$.

4. Chimera state in coupled q -deformed Lozi maps

Chimera states are dynamical patterns in which coherent and incoherent behaviours coexist in coupled identical systems. Multistability and rational or deformed dynamics provide a rich substrate for such complex spatiotemporal phenomena. Motivated by these features, we investigate chimera states in lattices of coupled q -deformed Lozi maps, showing that discrete-time systems with rational, deformed dynamics can also support robust chimera patterns. We doubly q -deform the Lozi map using the definition stated earlier in equations (4) and (5). Both variables are deformed in the same manner, $q = q_x = q_y$. We introduce one more variable $d = 1 - q$. The coupled map equations we use are as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x_{t+1}(i) &= (1 - \epsilon)f([x_t(i)]_q, [y_t(i)]_q) + \frac{\epsilon}{2}[f([x_t(i+1)]_q, [y_t(i+1)]_q) + f([x_t(i-1)]_q, [y_t(i-1)]_q)], \\ y_{t+1}(i) &= g([x_t(i)]_q, [y_t(i)]_q) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

where $x_t(i)$ is a continuous variable value at site i at discrete time t . Here, $i=1,2 \dots, N$. The q -deformed x and y variables are given by Eq. (4) and (5).

We proceed with Lozi map parameters fixed at $a = 1.7$ and $b = 0.5$. We study the spatiotemporal dynamical properties under the presence of the deformation parameter q with variation of the coupling strength ϵ for the above system. We investigate three cases (a) $d = 1 - q = 0.1$, (b) $d = 1 - q = 0.3$ and (c) $d = 1 - q = 0.5$. We study the bifurcation diagram, spatiotemporal evolution, and nature of the attractor.

4.1. Deformation parameter $d = 0.1$

A bifurcation diagram is a visual representation that shows how the qualitative behaviour of a dynamical system changes as a system parameter is varied. We plot the bifurcation diagram showing the long-time behaviour of $x(i)$ with respect to the coupling parameter ϵ in Fig.1. ϵ spans range $[-1:1.5]$ and q -deformation parameter is $d = 1 - q = 0.1$. Here, $q_x = q_y = q$. We observe a transition from a chaotic state to periodic behaviour through successive branch splitting. For negative values of ϵ , the points are widely scattered along the $x_i(t)$ axis, indicating a chaotic regime. As ϵ

FIG. 1. (Color online) The bifurcation diagram for a coupled doubly q -deformed Lozi map with deformation parameter $d = 1 - q = 0.1$ over a range of coupling strengths $\epsilon \in [-1:1.5]$. The diagram shows a transition from chaos to periodic behaviour through successive branch splitting.

approaches zero, the scatter begins to organise into multiple distinct branches, signalling the onset of bifurcation. For positive values of ϵ , the points form separate, discrete lines, which correspond to periodic or quasi-periodic states.

The space-time plot for $N = 100$, $d = 1 - q = 0.1$ and $\epsilon = 0.81$ is plotted after dropping 19000 transients as shown in Fig.2(a). The space-time plot shows vertical columns of varying widths and with different features. It is evident that different sites have different qualitative behaviour. The time series for map index i is a plot of sites $x_i(t)$ versus time t . We plot time series for $i = 21, 52, 75$ and 83 for a few time steps as seen in Fig.2(b). The figure illustrates that all sites exhibit sustained oscillatory behaviour with bounded amplitudes, indicating that the system has reached a stable dynamical regime. Although the oscillations of different sites have similar periodicity, their amplitudes and phases differ, reflecting partial synchronisation rather than complete synchronisation among the nodes. The spatial profile can be shown by plotting $x_i(t)$

versus map index i as shown in Fig.2(c). It reveals pronounced spatial variations across the network, with $x_i(t)$ exhibiting oscillatory behaviour and non-uniform amplitudes along i . While several sites display similar values, localised deviations and sharp drops are observed for specific indices, indicating spatial incoherence.

In Fig.3 we plot the chaotic attractors for sites $i = 21, 52, 75$ and 83 . Sites $i = 21$ and $i = 52$ evolve on compact, well-localised sets, indicating regular periodic or weakly chaotic motion. In contrast, $i = 75$ displays a widely spread and irregular trajectory, characteristic of chaotic dynamics. Site $i = 83$ forms two distinct clusters in phase space, suggesting multistability or switching between coexisting attractors. The coexistence of localised periodic attractors and extended chaotic attractors across different sites demonstrates strong spatial heterogeneity and supports the presence of chimera-like behaviour in the coupled system.

4.2. Deformation parameter $d=0.3$

In a similar manner, we plot the bifurcation diagram for $d = 1 - q = 0.3$, which is presented in Fig.4. The diagram demonstrates a rich sequence of chaos–order–chaos transitions driven by the control parameter ϵ . For $\epsilon < 0$, the system exhibits a highly scattered distribution of points, indicating a chaotic regime with large amplitude fluctuations. As ϵ approaches zero, the chaotic cloud collapses into a narrow band, signalling a transition toward an ordered state. For intermediate positive values of ϵ , stable periodic windows are observed, characterised by well-defined branches. However, as ϵ increases further, these ordered structures destabilise and expand into a broad chaotic region again, indicating a reverse transition from periodic dynamics to chaos.

The spatio-temporal plot for $N = 100$ and $\epsilon = 0.823$ after dropping 19000 transients is shown in Fig.5(a). The figure reveals persistent stripe-like patterns that extend uniformly along

FIG. 2. (Color online) (a) The spatio-temporal evolution of $N=100$ sites shows different qualitative behaviour for different sites. (b) Shows the temporal evolution for sites $i = 21, 52, 75$ and 83 . All four sites exhibit sustained oscillatory behaviour with bounded amplitude. (c) Shows the spatial distribution of the variable $x_i(t)$ as a function of the site index i at a fixed time $t = 2 \times 10^4$. Note that for all plots for $d = 1 - q = 0.1$ and $\epsilon = 0.81$.

the time axis, indicating temporally periodic dynamics. At the same time, the presence of distinct vertical bands across specific indices suggests spatial clustering, where groups of sites exhibit similar dynamical behaviour. The absence

of complete uniformity across the spatial domain indicates that the system does not reach full synchronisation.

We plot the time series for map index i for $i = 19, 25, 40$ and 70 over the time interval

FIG. 3. (Color online) Attractors for sites $i = 21, 52, 75$ and 83 for $d = 0.1$ and $\epsilon = 0.81$. All four sites have reached different attractors, implying the existence of *chimera*.

FIG. 4. (Color online) The bifurcation diagram for coupled doubly q -deformed Lozi map as a function coupling strength ϵ in the range $[-1:3]$ for the deformation parameter $d = 1 - q = 0.3$. We observe a transition from chaos to successive periodic splitting, which is again followed by chaos.

$t = 19100$ to 19150 , as shown in Fig.5(b). After the transient dynamics have decayed, all sites exhibit sustained oscillations with bounded amplitudes, indicating the emergence of a stable

long-term dynamical regime. The system does not achieve complete synchronisation. Instead, the coexistence of coherent oscillatory behaviour with site-dependent variations suggests partial or cluster synchronisation. The spatial profile is shown by plotting $x_i(t)$ versus map index i in Fig.5(c) at a fixed time $t = 2 \times 10^4$. We observe strong spatial heterogeneity. Extended regions with relatively smooth variations coexist with highly irregular segments characterised by rapid fluctuations and large amplitude jumps. This coexistence of coherent and incoherent spatial domains indicates that the system does not reach global synchronisation.

Fig.6 displays the phase-space projections for four representative sites ($i = 19, 25, 40$, and 70). The trajectories occupy bounded yet irregular regions, confirming the existence of strange attractors in the system dynamics. Sites $i = 25$ and $i = 40$ evolve on overlapping but densely populated regions, indicating similar chaotic dynamics and partial synchronisation. In contrast, site $i = 19$ explores a broader and more dispersed region of phase space, reflecting stronger chaotic behaviour, site $i = 70$ exhibits compact clusters embedded within the chaotic cloud, suggesting intermittent switching between coherent motion and chaotic excursions. Different dynamical characteristics establish the existence of *chimera*.

4.3. Deformation parameter $d=0.5$

The bifurcation diagram for the deformation parameter $d = 1 - q = 0.5$ is shown in Fig.7 over the coupling parameter ϵ in the range $[-0.5:2]$. For small values of ϵ , the system evolves toward a stable fixed point, indicating coherent and stationary dynamics. As ϵ increases, the fixed point loses stability, and a sequence of bifurcations emerges, leading to periodic oscillations. Further increase in ϵ results in period-doubling cascades, clearly visible as the splitting of branches, which ultimately give rise to chaotic dynamics. In the large- ϵ regime,

FIG. 5. (Color online) (a) Shows the spatio-temporal evolution of sites $N = 100$. We observe that different sites exhibit different qualitative behaviour. (b) Shows the temporal evolution for sites $i = 19, 25, 40$ and 70 . All four sites exhibit sustained oscillation with bound amplitude. (c) Shows the spatial distribution of the variable $x_i(t)$ as a function of the site index i at a fixed time $t = 2 \times 10^4$. We observe strong spatial heterogeneity. Note that for all plots:- $d = 1 - q = 0.3$ and $\epsilon = 0.823$.

the dense and widely scattered distribution of points signifies fully developed chaos with large-amplitude fluctuations.

We present the space-time plot for $N = 100$ and $\epsilon = 0.84$ after discarding 19000 transients,

as shown in Fig.8(a). The plot reveals persistent vertical stripe-like structures, indicating that groups of sites maintain similar dynamical behaviour over time. The absence of complete uniformity along the spatial direction highlights

FIG. 6. (Color online) For $d = 1 - q = 0.3$ and $\epsilon = 0.823$ we plot the attractors obtained for sites $i = 19, 25, 40$ and 70 . Since different sites exhibit different dynamical characteristic attractors, we can ascertain the presence of *chimera*.

FIG. 7. (Color online) Bifurcation diagram for coupled doubly q -deformed Lozi map as a function coupling parameter ϵ in the range $[-0.5:2]$ for deformation parameter $d = 1 - q = 0.5$. We observe stationary dynamics, followed by periodic cascade and chaos.

the co-existence of coherent and incoherent regions. A plot of time series has been made for these values of ϵ and d for sites $i = 6, 21, 46$ and 85 in Fig.8(b). The time series exhibits oscillatory dynamics with comparable frequencies but distinct amplitudes and phases across

different sites. The phase differences among the oscillations suggest partial synchronisation rather than complete coherence. The spatial profile can be shown by plotting $x_i(t)$ versus map index i at a fixed time $t = 2 \times 10^4$, as in Fig.8(c). It reveals strong spatial heterogeneity. Regions of relatively smooth variation coexist with segments that display rapid fluctuations and large amplitude jumps, indicating spatial incoherence. Such a nonuniform distribution of $x_i(t)$ suggests partial synchronisation, where coherent and incoherent domains coexist simultaneously.

In Fig.9, we plot attractors for the sites mentioned above. Distinct geometrical structures are observed for different sites, indicating site-dependent dynamical behaviour. While some sites evolve on relatively compact and well-defined attractors, others display broader and more scattered trajectories, reflecting higher dynamical complexity. The coexistence of localised clusters and dispersed point clouds suggests partial synchronisation, with simultaneous presence of coherent and incoherent dynamics. Such heterogeneous phase space structures are characteristic of chimeras.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we investigate the emergence of chimera-type states in a locally coupled map lattice composed of q -deformed Lozi maps. The map parameters were fixed at $a = 1.7$ and $b = 0.5$, while the system dynamics were explored by introducing the deformation parameter $d = 1 - q$ and varying the coupling strength ϵ . Three representative values of the deformation parameter, namely $d = 0.1, 0.3$, and 0.5 , were considered to examine the role of deformation on collective dynamics. This work extends the theory of chimera states to a new class of dynamical systems by demonstrating their existence in networks of coupled q -deformed Lozi maps. By incorporating the Jaganathan-Sinha deformation scheme, the local dynamics become rational and tunable

FIG. 8. (Color online) Different plots for $d = 1 - q = 0.5$ and $\epsilon = 0.84$. (a) Shows the spatio-temporal evolution of sites $N = 100$. The absence of complete uniformity along the spatial direction highlights the co-existence of coherent and incoherent regions. (b) Shows the time evolution for sites $i = 6, 21, 46$ and 85 . All four sites exhibit sustained oscillations, but distinct amplitude. (c) Shows the spatial profile at $t = 2 \times 10^4$. The spatial profile depicts a non-uniform distribution of $x(i)$.

through a deformation parameter, offering a novel mechanism for controlling collective behaviour. The bifurcation diagrams reveal that increasing the coupling strength induces a transition from coherent behaviour to complex spatio-temporal

dynamics, with the deformation parameter significantly influencing the onset and nature of these transitions. Space-time plots clearly demonstrate the coexistence of coherent and incoherent domains over a wide range of coupling

FIG. 9. (Color online) For $d = 1 - q = 0.5$ and $\epsilon = 0.84$, we plot attractors obtained for the sites $i = 6, 21, 46$ and 85 . We perceive the appearance of *chimera* as different sites reach different attractors.

strengths. The chimera state is known to exist in systems with non-local connections. However, the results show that chimera states can arise under purely local coupling even when the underlying dynamics is non-standard and deformed, thereby reinforcing the robustness and universality of chimera phenomena. Moreover, the deformation parameter provides an additional degree of

freedom to manipulate stability, bifurcation structure, and transitions between coherent and incoherent states, which is not available in conventional coupled map lattices.

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Data Availability Statement

All data supporting the plots presented in this paper and the other findings of the study are available from the first author upon reasonable request.

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